

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Modelling The Fracture Energy of Polymer Nanocomposites

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Background

Experimental Results: Quasi-static Mode I toughness

Intrinsic Mechanisms

Extrinsic Mechanisms

Modelling

Conclusion

1 Background

Relatively low toughness

And

Poor cyclic fatigue resistance

Can led to **rapid** and **large-scale** cracking.

2 Materials and Method

3.1 Experimental Results: G_{Ic}

- **Linear increase** up to a nanofiller concentration of 1.5 wt.%
- Toughness **increase is larger for CNF** compared to GNP and hybrid counterparts.
- Difference due to **extent of toughening** mechanisms induced.

3.2 Intrinsic Mechanisms

Unmodified

- No microscale damage in process zone
- Well-defined crack tip
- No evidence of intrinsic or extrinsic toughening mechanism.

CNF Doped

- ← Microscale damage in process zone for CNF and GNP composites →
- Interfacial debonding CNFs and epoxy)

GNP Doped

- Interfacial debonding (GNPs and epoxy)

3.3 Intrinsic Mechanisms

CNF and Epoxy Plastic Void Growth

GNP and Epoxy Plastic Void Growth

3.4 Intrinsic Mechanisms: Prominence

- 1. GNP microcracking
- 2. Nanofiller-epoxy interfacial debonding
- 3. Microcrack coalescence

} ↑ Relatively minor toughening mechanisms

- 4. Plastic void growth
Due to significantly higher elastic modulus of nano filler compared to epoxy.

} ↑↑↑ Prominent toughening mechanism

3.5 Extrinsic Mechanisms

CNF Crack-Bridging

GNP Crack-Bridging

3.6 Summary

4.1 Model: CNF, GNP and Hybrid

$$G_{Ic} = G_{CU} + \Delta G_{pull-out} + \Delta G_{rupture} + \Delta G_{db} + \Delta G_v$$

$$G_{Ic,CNF} = G_{CU} + \frac{V_f \sigma_f^2 d_f}{8\tau_i} + \frac{V_f \sigma_f^2 l_f}{2E_f} + \frac{V_f l_{po} G_i}{d_f} + \left(1 + \frac{\mu_m}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 V_f \left(\frac{d_v^2}{3d_f^2} + \frac{d_v}{3d_f} - \frac{2}{3}\right) \sigma_y r_{yu} K_{vm}^2$$

$$G_{Ic,GNP} = G_{CU} + \frac{V_f t W \sigma^2}{2(t+W)\tau_G} + \frac{V_f l \sigma^2}{2E_G} + \frac{2V_f(t+W)l_{po}G_i}{tW} + \left(1 + \frac{\mu_m}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 [V_{void} - V_f] \sigma_y r_{yu} K_{vm}^2$$

+

$$G_{Ic,Hybrid} = V_{f,CNF} (G_{Ic,CNF}) + V_{f,GNP} (G_{Ic,GNP})$$

4.2 Modelling and Experiment

- Predictions by the model in accord, except until increase in agglomeration

- Prominence of Mechanisms

No significant interactions between the two nanofillers with respect to the toughening mechanisms

Conclusion

The **effects of the shape** and concentration of nanoscale carbon fillers on the quasi-static fracture energy

Results show **improvements to the mode I fracture energy, G_{Ic}**

Major **intrinsic** toughening mechanisms: (a) debonding of the nanofillers, (b) plastic void growth initiated by the debonded nanofillers,

Major **extrinsic** toughening mechanisms (c) pull-out and crack bridging of the nanofillers; and (d) rupture of the bridging nanofillers.

Modelling the toughening mechanisms demonstrated to predict fracture energy, G_{Ic} , showed **good agreement** with experimental results.

$$G_{Ic,CNF} = G_{CU} + \frac{V_f \sigma_f^2 d_f}{8\tau_i} + \frac{V_f \sigma_f^2 l_f}{2E_f} + \frac{V_f l_{po} G_i}{d_f} + \left(1 + \frac{\mu_m}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 V_f \left(\frac{d_v^2}{3d_f^2} + \frac{d_v}{3d_f} - \frac{2}{3}\right) \sigma_y r_{yu} K_{vm}^2$$

$$G_{Ic,GNP} = G_{CU} + \frac{V_f t W \sigma^2}{2(t+W)\tau_G} + \frac{V_f l \sigma^2}{2E_G} + \frac{2V_f(t+W)l_{po} G_i}{tW} + \left(1 + \frac{\mu_m}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 [V_{void} - V_f] \sigma_y r_{yu} K_{vm}^2$$

Acknowledgments

RESEARCH SPONSORED BY AUSTRALIAN RESEARCH COUNCIL DISCOVERY GRANT AND RMIT UNIVERSITY.

RESEARCH SUPPORT

- Dr. Raj Ladani, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
- Distinguished Professor Adrian P. Mouritz, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
- Professor Chun H. Wang, UNSW, Sydney, Australia
- Professor Anthony J. Kinloch, Imperial College London, U.K.
- Dr. Shuying Wu, Macquarie University, Sydney, Australia
- Anil Raj Ravindran, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

TECHNICAL SUPPORT

- Robert Ryan
- Peter Tkatchyk
- Julian Bradler
- Mr. Phil Francis and Dr. Mathew Field

Thanks !

Relevant Reference:

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